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**Symmetry Theory-Based Approaches for the Computation of Mode Shapes of
Vibrating Structures**

Direct doctoral research proposal submitted to FAPESP.
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Abstract

The study of vibrating elastic bodies plays a crucial role in the dynamic analysis of engineering problems. For that, displacement patterns of vibrating systems, i.e., mode shapes, have shown great importance for assessing their motion behavior, whose modeling arises from differential equations. Symmetry methods assist the exact solution of differential equations through analytical transformations such as order reductions, domain compression, and linearizations. This research proposal addresses the computation of mode shapes of uniform and non-uniform rods, Euler-Bernoulli beams, Timoshenko beams, and rectangular plates via symmetry methods. Prior investigation shows that the Lie symmetry method originally accomplishes exact mode shapes of non-uniform rods and accurate ones for uniform Euler-Bernoulli beams, free from round-off errors when numerically assessed at all frequencies. Also, this method provides expressions for mode shapes of uniform rectangular plates, namely invariant solutions, that may be superimposed to develop original mode shape solutions. On the other hand, the Lie symmetry method has been found inefficient for other generic non-uniform cases due to their modeling equations with arbitrary functions. Within this framework, this proposal suggests an extension of the previous mode shape studies through better-conditioned symmetry methods for differential equations with arbitrary functions, e.g., the generalized symmetry method, producing new vibroacoustic applications, enhancing prediction, simulation, and design capabilities of real complex problems just as periodic and metamaterial structures. This proposal provides an overview of the research topics, the scientific motivation, the candidate's prior results on the field, the work plan, and the candidate's skills.

Keywords: Mode shapes. Exact solutions. Lie symmetries. Generalized symmetries. Rods. Euler-Bernoulli beams. Timoshenko beams. Plates. Periodic structures.

1 Motivation

Vibration analysis has been proven essential to modern engineering concerning product safety, design, and efficiency (YU; GILLOT; ICHCHOU, 2013; PEETERS; ROECK, 2001; DOEBLING; FARRAR; PRIME, 1998; MAIA, 1997). The Theory of Vibration governs the modeling of vibrating structures through differential equations (DEs), whose mathematical complexity, in general, follows the level of reality and structural sophistication represented by the model (WANG; REDDY; LEE, 2000; WEAVER; TIMOSHENKO; YOUNG, 1990; RAYLEIGH, 1945). Accordingly, the requirement for complicated DEs may reduce the utilization of accurate models essentially due to the difficulty of solving them (WU *et al.*, 2018; ZHU; LI, 2017; PAOLA *et al.*, 2013; REDDY, 2007). As long as the feasibility of some models relies on that, it is worth mentioning the importance of studying solution methods for DEs.

Computational advances brought fruitful numerical solution methods (BUTCHER, 2016; CHAPRA; CANALE, 2021; BHATTI, 2006; AMES, 1977). Then, the assessment of approximate solutions became a routine task for predicting the behavior of vibrating structures, especially regarding complex ones (RENSON; KERSCHEN; COCHELIN, 2016; XIANG; YANG, 2008; NOOR; BURTON; BERT, 1996; NARAYANAN; BESKOS, 1982). However, exact analytical solutions still play critical roles in engineering problems, such as optimization and computational time reduction (BERGER; WADLEY; MCMEEKING, 2017; DOWELL; HALL, 2001; MEAD, 1996; EISENBERGER, 1991). The point is, analytical methods frequently require robust mathematical tools for solving DEs, which leads to the incorrect belief of merely fitting simple problems (AMES, 1972; MURPHY, 1960).

Meanwhile, computational development also embodied symbolic software and computer algebra, enabling well-founded algebraic methods to be applied more efficiently for the exact resolution of intricate DEs (RAYNA, 2013; HOLT; EICK; O'BRIEN, 2005; WOLFRAM, 2003). Symmetry methods have been gaining more attention recently for such reasons indeed (STEINBERG; JUNIOR, 2014; CHEVIAKOV, 2007; BAUMANN, 2000). Generally speaking, symmetry methods encompass a variety of procedures based on transformations of coordinates for classifying, simplifying, and solving DEs. Each method deals with different kinds of mathematical symmetries, e.g., Lie symmetries, Lie-Bäcklund symmetries, nonlocal, and generalized symmetries (BLUMAN; CHEVIAKOV; ANCO, 2010; CANTWELL, 2002). Among them, the Lie symmetry method provided the first well-founded mathematical theory on symmetry analysis for DEs. Lie symmetries expose potential transformations that retain equations' solutions invariant and allow straightforward constructions of exact solutions by analytical order reductions, linearizations, and domain compressions (BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002; OLVER, 1986).

When dealing with continuous bodies, the assumption of harmonic motion allows removing their models' time dependency and expressing the associated dynamic behavior in terms of displacement patterns, the so-called mode shapes. Assessing how the structure behaves spatially, i.e., solving its mode shape equations, simplifies building time-dependent solutions (RAO, 2019; INMAN, 2013; BLEVINS, 1979). Few exact solutions are known for mode shape equations of complicated structures made up of non-uniform, periodic, and metamaterial structures, where the associated DEs may prevent analytical studies for determining vibration properties by ordinary approaches (SAEIDIFAR; OHADI, 2010; KUMAR; SUJITH, 1997; ABRATE, 1995). Despite providing powerful tools for solving intricate DEs, symmetry method applications for mode shape equations are barely observed in the literature (NUNES; SILVA; MENCIK, 2019).

Concerning productivity and efficiency, non-uniform structures allow high versatility for fitting required geometry and dynamic behavior in vibroacoustic engineering applications (WU; CHANG; LIN, 2009; DYLEJKO *et al.*, 2007). In the same way, periodic structures are convenient for vibration reduction purposes, where wave interactions along identical cells connected

repeated times produce band gaps, i.e., frequency ranges in which internally reflected waves attenuate vibration (SANTOS, 2018; BRILLOUIN, 1953). Periodic structures are also significant in metamaterial design, structures formed by synthetic combinations of inclusions and periodicity (ALADWANI; ALMANDEEL; NOUH, 2019; BELI; ARRUDA; RUZZENE, 2018). Displacement patterns variation in periodic structures is an attractive topic relating them to the study of mode shapes. These variations for periodic structures occur due to periodicity break, e.g., irregularities from the manufacturing process and damages during operation, whose identification consists of a tool for structural health monitoring (PAIXÃO *et al.*, 2020; TIMORIAN *et al.*, 2019; DOEBLING; FARRAR; PRIME, 1998; PANDEY; BISWAS; SAMMAN, 1991). Conversely, geometrical and material discontinuities yield mathematical models with high complexity, including designed ones for vibration reduction and not desired ones from damages. Knowing that a few resolution techniques for these models consider analytical approaches, original and efficient solutions may arise from the inherent properties of symmetry methods (BELI *et al.*, 2018; YANG *et al.*, 2014; XIAO *et al.*, 2013).

Within this framework, current master's study of the candidate Afonso Nunes deals with the computation of exact mode shape solutions for vibration models of rods, beams, and plates via Lie symmetries, an unexplored topic in the literature through symmetry methods. The focus consists in examining such models for non-uniform structures, although the investigation of uniform ones also provides original advances regarding their dynamic analysis. The following paragraphs address the accomplishments of this ongoing study, better detailed in the candidate's Qualification Exam Report¹ presented to the Mechanical Engineering Department of São Paulo State University and attached to SAGE.

Exact mode shape expressions for the longitudinal vibration of uniform rods are already documented in the literature (GERADIN, 2015; CLOUGH, 2003). These solutions have no issues regarding instabilities, singular points, or boundary conditions (BCs). For non-uniform rods, i.e., rods with varying cross-section area functions, densities, and Young's moduli², there are no general closed-form solutions in the literature such as the exact ones for uniform rods (GUO; YANG, 2011a; RAJ; SUJITH, 2005; RAMAN, 1983). The admitted Lie symmetries of the second-order ordinary differential equation (ODE) for the mode shapes of a given non-uniform rod provide it with an order reduction, converting it into a Riccati equation, i.e., a first-order ODE. Different from the original ODE, the reduced-order equation possesses ad hoc solution methods. Original closed-form solutions arise from the resolution of this Riccati equation when considering specific cross-section variations (this procedure also retrieves exact solutions documented in the literature). These results will be submitted to the Journal of Sound and Vibration with Prof. Dr. Adrián S. Ruiz's collaboration from the University of Cádiz, Spain.

¹<https://www.dropbox.com/sh/rvxfba7palzuyam/AAAUNHiv3sIg4gBoAcgMiv6va?dl=0>

²The mode shape equation for rods with only varying cross-section area functions matches the non-uniform rods' case by a change of variables (GUO; YANG, 2011b). Thus, their equivalent mathematical form allows studying the first and simpler equation and deriving results for the remaining one as shown in Section 3.

Closed-form solutions for mode shapes of uniform Euler-Bernoulli beams are available in the literature (INMAN, 2013; WANG; REDDY; LEE, 2000). When it comes to high frequencies³, in general above the 12th beam's natural frequency, the numerical assessment of these mode shape expressions leads to round-off errors, which arise from floating-point arithmetic operations between closely similar large values. These round-off errors can be seen by plotting high-order mode shapes of a given beam against the position of the vibrating structure. Thus, such popular closed-form solutions are ill-conditioned when numerically evaluated. Recently, the use of mathematical identities for rewriting these mode shape solutions has prevented numerical instabilities (GONÇALVES *et al.*, 2019; KHASAWNEH; SEGALMAN, 2019; GONÇALVES; PEPLow; BRENNAN, 2018). On the other hand, the Lie symmetry method can provide well-posed problems using new spaces of variables. The computation of new spaces considering classical and non-classical BCs gave rise to naturally stable mode shapes of uniform Euler-Bernoulli beams. From these expressions, there are no concerns about round-off errors of the new mode shape expressions when numerically evaluated from low to high frequencies. This approach has been submitted to Acta Mechanica journal in the form of a manuscript⁴ in collaboration with Prof. Dr. Jean-Mathieu Mencik from the Institut National des Sciences Appliquées Centre Val de Loire, France, and Prof. Dr. Paulo J. Paupitz Gonçalves from São Paulo State University.

The investigation of Lie symmetry transformations brought new invariant solutions for the mode shape equation of uniform rectangular plates. Each invariant solution is related to a reduced-order ODE from symmetry transformations for the governing equation of the problem. By now, these solutions represent the possibility of building original exact mode shape expressions for BVPs of rectangular plates. This approach is being studied in collaboration with Prof. Dr. Adrián S. Ruiz. A noteworthy fact is that there are no exact mode shape solutions for several BVPs of vibrating rectangular plates, the most popular approaches deal with approximate symbolic solutions, e.g., by the Ritz-Rayleigh Method, or numerical methods (GERADIN, 2015; LEISSA, 1973; WARBURTON, 1954).

In the matter of non-uniform beams and plates with arbitrary cross-sections, the achieved Lie symmetries were able to reduce the associated mode shape equations' order by one. These reduced-order equations are not as convenient for computing closed-form solutions as the Riccati equation for non-uniform rods is. The arbitrary functions from the mode shape equations allow computing a unique explicit Lie symmetry transformation and, hence, a single order reduction. This lack of admitted Lie symmetries prevents the complete integration and resolution of these equations by the method (MENDOZA; MURIEL, 2021). The limited action of the computed Lie symmetry transformations leads to an inefficient approach for these non-uniform cases keeping arbitrary functions invariant. Conversely, different kinds of mathematical sym-

³The Euler-Bernoulli beam model can represent waves of wavelength six times greater than the thickness of slender beams without significant accuracy reduction (FAHY, 2006). In addition, high-order mode shape applications have been helpful for computing mode shapes of rectangular plates (WARBURTON, 1954).

⁴https://www.dropbox.com/sh/r4acs6gu7cn7khp/AACrA8ugN_ValeGGIUNTBzG9a?dl=0

metries may act on broader spaces of variables, e.g., including derivatives and integrals of dependent variables or unknown functions (BLUMAN; CHEVIAKOV, 2005; FLIESS *et al.*, 1999; IBRAGIMOV; KARA; MAHOMED, 1998). More general symmetries such as generalized and lambda-symmetries can be helpful regarding cases with arbitrary expressions (RUIZ; MURIEL, 2018; MURIEL; ROMERO; RUIZ, 2017).

Given the investigation of mode shapes of rods, both Euler-Bernoulli and Timoshenko beams, and plates through the Lie symmetry method, the obtained results and identified inefficiencies, a natural extension for the research concerns evaluating non-uniform cases using “better conditioned” symmetry methods for equations with arbitrary functions. Recent symmetry techniques may deal with the found inefficiencies of the previous approach. Thus, this research project proposes a study of such symmetry techniques for solving complex vibration problems, focusing on the generalized symmetry method (MURIEL; ROMERO; OLVER, 2006; MURIEL, 2001). On top of that, the candidate has accomplished proficiency on Lie symmetry methods, which is a positive aspect regarding the project’s timeline once new symmetry techniques share invariance concepts and mathematical tools with the Lie symmetry method. The study on generalized symmetries relates this project to Prof. Dr. María C. Muriel Patino’s research, from the University of Cádiz, who proposed the generalized symmetry theory, and Prof. Dr. Adrián S. Ruiz, who has been working in the same subject. The research from this doctoral project could reach greater results during a BEPE internship supervised by any of these mathematicians. Within this framework, a BEPE internship from 6 to 12 months at the University of Cádiz could assist with grasping the mathematical theory of generalized symmetries and contribute to new collaborations. Prof. Dr. Adrián S. Ruiz indicated through a recommendation letter⁵ being glad to host the candidate there, also attached to SAGe.

It is worth mentioning that the presented results have been part of a research maturing process since the first 12 months of scientific initiation granted by FAPESP, process 2016/22473 – 6, where the candidate started learning the Lie symmetry method for studying static deflection beam problems. This research step gave a great background on Lie symmetry computations for ODEs. For the 12 following months of scholarship, associated with the same process, the analysis of wave propagation problems under the Lie symmetry view provided a good understanding of symmetry methods for partial differential equations (PDEs) and initial and boundary value problems (IBVPs). The study on Lie symmetries of PDEs supported the current investigation for the mode shape equation of uniform rectangular plates. During the internship and supervised both by Prof. Dr. Samuel da Silva and Prof. Dr. Jean-Mathieu Mencik, the candidate studied symmetry applications for mode shape equations, finding the literature gap and eventually resulting in this proposal. The awareness of invariant BCs from the latter provided the idea of looking for numerically stable mode shape expressions for Euler-Bernoulli beams, recently

⁵https://www.dropbox.com/sh/w3m7nnaagmuupv/AACy0l8vTXdBfgEfyxz2-_ySa?dl=0

submitted to the journal *Acta Mecanica*. In the meantime, the candidate's BEPE scholarship, grant number 2018/21734-6, contributed to the collaboration of Prof. Dr. Jean-Mathieu Mencik in the research.

The main originality of this doctorate proposition regards the computation of exact solutions for vibration models of non-uniform structures. A few accurate mode shape solutions are available in the literature for these structures, which, when reported, consider certain cross-section variations that turn mode shape equations into mathematical forms whose closed-form are already known. In this sense, the symmetry approach represents the possibility of solving intricate problems initially, based on well-founded mathematical techniques. Also, broadening the study on symmetry methods for mechanical vibration problems enhances the barely seen applications of such powerful methods for solving engineering problems.

2 Goals

This research proposal intends to provide a symmetry study for computing new exact solutions for the mode shape equations of uniform and non-uniform structures for vibroacoustic applications, such as rods, beams, and plates, improving the capacity of prediction, simulation, and design of periodic structures.

3 Vibration of Rods, Beams and Plates

This section presents the vibration models for rods, Euler-Bernoulli beams, Timoshenko beams, and rectangular plates, their respective mode shape equations, and discussions on mode shape solutions from the literature when available.

3.1 Longitudinal vibration of rods

The motion equation for rods with non-uniform cross-sections undergoing free longitudinal vibrating follows as (INMAN, 2013; KINSLER *et al.*, 1999):

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(E S \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \tilde{u}(x, t) \right) - \rho S \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \tilde{u}(x, t) = 0, \quad x \in]l_1, l_2[, \quad t > 0, \quad (1)$$

where $E = E(x)$ is the Young's modulus of the rod, $S = S(x)$ is its cross-section area function, and $\rho = \rho(x)$ is its density. Furthermore, $\tilde{u}(x, t)$ is the rod's time-dependent longitudinal displacement, $x \in [l_1, l_2]$ represents the position along the structure, and $t \geq 0$ denotes time.

By introducing the new variable (GUO; YANG, 2011b; ZHONG; NIE, 1997):

$$y = \int_0^x \left(\frac{\rho(\tau)/\rho_0}{E(\tau)/E_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} d\tau,$$

the motion equation becomes:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(E_0 \bar{S} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \tilde{u}(y, t) \right) - \rho_0 \bar{S} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \tilde{u}(y, t) = 0, \quad (2)$$

for E_0 and ρ_0 being the Young's modulus and the density of the rod at its cross-section labeled as the origin, respectively, and $\bar{S} = (E \rho / E_0 \rho_0)^{\frac{1}{2}} S$. When considering rods with only varying cross-section areas, i.e., $E = E_0$ and $\rho = \rho_0$, the new variable turns into $y = x$ and Eq. (2) yields:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(E_0 S \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \tilde{u}(x, t) \right) - \rho_0 S \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \tilde{u}(x, t) = 0. \quad (3)$$

Eqs. (2) and (3) have equivalent mathematical forms. Thus, solutions for non-uniform rods can be derived from the latter's solutions, an easier DE, by a simple change of variable following the relations for y and \bar{S} . Hereafter, Eq. (3) will be considered for obtaining the mode shape equation for non-uniform rods.

Let $\tilde{u} = u e^{i\omega t}$ be a harmonic non-trivial solution, where $u = u(x)$ and ω are the mode shape functions and the natural angular frequencies of the rod, respectively. From this, Eq. (3) can be written as the mode shape equation as follows:

$$\frac{1}{S} \frac{d}{dx} \left(S \frac{du}{dx} \right) + \lambda_0^2 u = 0, \quad (4)$$

where $\lambda_0 = (\rho_0 / E_0)^{\frac{1}{2}} \omega$ is the wavenumber⁶.

Concerning mode shape solutions for non-uniform rods, the authors Guo and Yang (2011b) provide series solutions for four profiles of rods, including quadratic, exponential, trigonometric, and hyperbolic functions. A specific quadratic variation had been previously considered by Abrate (1995), deriving an exact solution for given BVPs of rods. Kumar and Sujith (1997) computed closed-form solutions considering cases of polynomials and quadratic, trigonometric functions, and Raj and Sujith (2005) for exponential cross-sectional variations. Distinct approaches include the exact element method (EISENBERGER, 1991), change of variables⁷ for converting mode shape equations in Schroedinger, Sturm-Liouville equations, and Legendre equations (YARDIMOGLU; AYDIN, 2011; RAMAN, 1983), and the differential transformation method (ZENG; BERT, 2001).

⁶Purely longitudinal waves only propagate in unbounded solid media when the two perpendicular motion directions are sizable. Once the rod's model assumes exclusive longitudinal vibration for thin structures, the term *quasi*-longitudinal wavenumber is more accurate. (FAHY, 2006).

⁷Several changes of variables for DEs arise from symmetry transformations (CAPOZZIELLO; LAMBIASE, 2000; CLARKSON; OLVER, 1996). Without symmetry methods, changes of variables may appear randomly chosen.

3.2 Transverse vibration of Euler-Bernoulli beams

Slender beams undergoing free transverse vibration are modeled following the Euler-Bernoulli beam theory by the PDE (WANG; REDDY; LEE, 2000):

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \left(EI \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \tilde{u}(x, t) \right) + m \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \tilde{u}(x, t) = 0, \quad x \in]l_1, l_2[, \quad t > 0, \quad (5)$$

where $EI = EI(x)$ is the beam's flexural stiffness, $m = m(x)$ is its mass per unit length, $\tilde{u}(x, t)$ is the transverse displacement, $x \in [l_1, l_2]$ is the position along the beam, and $t \geq 0$ represents time. Similarly to the above-mentioned case for rods, the introduction of a harmonic solution in the motion equation leads to the mode shape equation for $u = u(x)$. In this case, Eq. (5) yields the following ODE for non-uniform beams (GERADIN, 2015):

$$\frac{d^2}{dx^2} \left(\frac{EI}{EI_0} \frac{d^2 u}{dx^2} \right) - \lambda_0 u = 0, \quad (6)$$

where EI_0 is the flexural stiffness for the beam's cross-section at $x=0$ and $\lambda_0 = (m\omega^2/EI_0)^{\frac{1}{4}}$. If one admits an uniform beam, in which all of its cross-sectional parameters are given as constants, Eq. (6) becomes (CLOUGH, 2003; KINSLER *et al.*, 1999):

$$\frac{d^4 u}{dx^4} - \lambda^4 u = 0, \quad (7)$$

for $\lambda = (m\omega^2/EI)^{\frac{1}{4}}$ being the wavenumber.

The classical exact solutions of Eq. (7) from the literature are usually prone to round-off errors when numerically evaluated at high frequencies (INMAN, 2013; WANG; REDDY; LEE, 2000). This might be explained since the hyperbolic functions from these solutions are becoming to be closely similar, i.e., with the same asymptotic behavior, as their exponential growth follows the frequency increasing, and operations between them cannot be accurately assessed by floating-point arithmetic. Numerical operations such as subtracting closer values may produce meaningless results due to the complete cancellation of significant digits (see Goldberg (1991) and Wilkinson (1994) for cancellation errors explanation in floating-point arithmetic). As such, the four equations from the given beam BCs are likely to yield inaccurate values for its natural frequencies and integration constants from the classical closed-form solution.

3.3 Transverse vibration of Timoshenko beams

The Timoshenko beam model includes effects of shearing forces and rotatory inertia in comparison to the Euler-Bernoulli model (LOVE, 2013). Thus, the inertia of the sections is no longer concentrated at the center of the beam, and the transverse shear is built in the model, which requires a correction on account of the assumption of constant shear stress along

the beam's cross-section. This correction is given by the so-called shear factor κ , whose value depends on properties of the beam, such as its geometry and material. From the Timoshenko model, the motion equations for the free transverse vibration of a beam are written as (CAZZANI; STOCHINO; TURCO, 2016; HUTCHINSON, 2000; TIMOSHENKO, 1922):

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[SG\kappa \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \tilde{u}(x, t) - \tilde{\phi}(x, t) \right) \right] - m \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \tilde{u}(x, t) = 0, \quad (8)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(EI \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \tilde{\phi}(x, t) \right) + SG\kappa \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \tilde{u}(x, t) - \tilde{\phi}(x, t) \right) - \rho I \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \tilde{\phi}(x, t) = 0, \quad x \in]l_1, l_2[, t > 0, \quad (9)$$

where $SG\kappa = SG\kappa(x)$ is the beam's shear stiffness, $\rho I = \rho I(x)$ is its rotational inertia per unit length, and G is the shear modulus. $\tilde{u}(x, t)$ stands for the transverse displacement, $\tilde{\phi}(x, t)$ is the cross-sectional's rotation, $x \in [l_1, l_2]$ is the position along the beam and $t \geq 0$ denotes time.

Considering harmonic solutions for Eqs. (8) and (9) just as $\tilde{u} = u e^{i\omega t}$ and $\tilde{\phi} = \phi e^{i\omega t}$. This yields (TAN *et al.*, 2018):

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left[SG\kappa \left(\phi - \frac{du}{dx} \right) \right] - m \omega^2 u = 0, \quad (10)$$

and

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(EI \frac{d\phi}{dx} \right) + SG\kappa \left(\frac{du}{dx} - \phi \right) + \rho I \omega^2 \phi = 0, \quad (11)$$

for the mode shapes $u = u(x)$ and $\phi = \phi(x)$.

Some of the fundamental solutions for non-uniform Timoshenko beams from the literature consider power series of circular frequency (LING *et al.*, 2018), the perturbation technique (EIPAKCHI; SOHANI, 2018), and the dynamic stiffness method (LEUNG; ZHOU, 1995) for obtaining solutions for special types of beams. Along with these methods, computing approximate solutions is still considered as a standard approach for vibrating Timoshenko beams (TORABI; AFSHARI; HEIDARI-RARANI, 2013; CLEGHORN; TABARROK, 1992; ROSSI; LAURA; GUTIERREZ, 1990). Studies on more complex problems such as coupled beams with flexible attachments, multiple discontinuities, and axially graded beams have also been performed (ZHAO; HUANG; GUO, 2017; ZHANG *et al.*, 2014). Furthermore, helpful closed-form series solutions were presented by the authors Chen and Ho (1998). However, there are several kinds of cross-section variations whose exact solutions are unknown.

3.4 Transverse vibration of rectangular plates

The free transverse vibration of a thin rectangular plate made of an isotropic material and with constant thickness can be modeled by the fourth-order partial differential equation (RAO,

2019; LOVE, 2013):

$$\frac{\partial^4 \tilde{w}}{\partial x^4} + 2 \frac{\partial^4 \tilde{w}}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^4 \tilde{w}}{\partial y^4} + \frac{12 \rho (1 - \nu^2)}{E h^2} \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{w}}{\partial t^2} = 0, \quad x \in]x_1, x_2[, \quad y \in]y_1, y_2[, \quad t > 0, \quad (12)$$

where $\tilde{w} = \tilde{w}(x, y, t)$ represents small displacements at the plate's perpendicular direction, the rectangular coordinates are $x \in]x_1, x_2]$ and $y \in]y_1, y_2]$, and $t \geq 0$ denotes time. For the plate's properties, ν is the Poisson's ration, and h is the thickness, ρ and E being constant.

When assuming harmonic solutions such as $\tilde{w} = w e^{i\omega t}$, where ω is the plate's angular frequency, the time dependency can be eliminated from Eq. (12). This procedure provides the so-called mode shape equation for the free transverse vibration of uniform rectangular plates:

$$\frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + 2 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial y^4} - \lambda^4 w = 0, \quad x \in]x_1, x_2[, \quad y \in]y_1, y_2[, \quad (13)$$

for the mode shape $w = w(x, y)$, where $\lambda = (\rho \omega^2 / D)^{\frac{1}{4}}$ is the wavenumber, and $D = E h^3 / [12(1 - \nu^2)]$ is the plate's flexural stiffness.

In the framework of computing mode shapes of uniform rectangular plates, Warburton (1954) has obtained symbolic, although approximate, solutions based on the Rayleigh-Ritz method for all possible BC configurations combining free, simply-supported (freely-supported), and clamped edges. Here, the author assumed Euler-Bernoulli beam mode shape functions as suitable waveforms. Once the Rayleigh-Ritz method imposes additional constraints to the model, the resulting frequencies are higher than those given by an accurate analysis. The accuracy of the presented approach is discussed by Warburton (1979). Leissa (1973) provided more accurate formulas than the expressions mentioned above, although still approximate ones. Recent books present an alternative approach based on independent solutions for the computation of mode shapes of rectangular plates (GERADIN, 2015; MEIROVITCH, 2010). However, it is worth mentioning that there are no exact solutions in the literature for several BC combinations, especially for non-classical ones such as springs and attached masses (ZEISSIG, 1898; VOIGT, 1893).

4 Lie Symmetry Theory

This section briefly introduces the procedure for computing Lie symmetries of systems of ODEs, order reductions, and the invariance formulation for BVPs. The presented procedure is interchangeable with ODEs and PDEs: taking a single dependent variable for the former and switching dependent and independent variables for the latter. The following describes the chosen multivariable notation for the symmetry method.

Consider the Lagrange's notation for derivatives:

$$z_j^{(k)} = \frac{d^k z_j}{dx^k},$$

for the k th-order derivative of $z_j = z_j(x)$. Thus, a system of n_d ODEs can be written as follows:

$$\mathcal{F}_n(x, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}^{\{1\}}, \dots, \mathbf{z}^{\{\sigma\}}) = 0 \quad (n = 1, 2, \dots, n_d), \quad (14)$$

where $\mathbf{z} = (z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{n_d})$ represents a set of dependent variables, $\mathbf{z}^{\{k\}}$ comprises all the k th-order derivatives of \mathbf{z} , and σ is highest derivative order in the system.

In short, the Lie symmetry theory provides groups of infinitesimal transformations for DEs as Eq. (14) that act on the (x, \mathbf{z}) -space of variables. These are the so-called Lie point transformations that depend on the infinitesimal functions $\xi = \xi(x, \mathbf{z})$ and $\eta_j = \eta_j(x, \mathbf{z})$, related to x and z_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n_d$), respectively. Extensions of Lie point transformations establish actions on the full DEs' space of variables, which includes all their derivatives. The prolongation formula for the k th-extended infinitesimal functions is given by (CANTWELL, 2002; OLVER, 1986):

$${}_{(k)}\eta_j = \mathcal{D}\left\{{}_{(k-1)}\eta_j\right\} - z_j^{(k)}\mathcal{D}\{\xi\}, \quad (15)$$

where ${}_{(0)}\eta_j = \eta_j$ and

$$\mathcal{D} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + z_\mu^{(1)}\frac{\partial}{\partial z_\mu} + \dots + z_\mu^{(\sigma)}\frac{\partial}{\partial z_\mu^{(\sigma-1)}}, \quad (16)$$

is the total derivative operator for the dummy index $\mu = n_d$, which follows the summation convention by Einstein notation⁸ (HARRISON; JOSEPH, 2016; EINSTEIN, 1916).

The operators known as infinitesimal generators are the standard way of representing the action of an infinitesimal transformation. For the k th-order extended infinitesimal transformation, the admitted prolonged infinitesimal generator is written as (BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002):

$${}_{(k)}\mathcal{X} = \xi\frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \eta_\mu\frac{\partial}{\partial z_\mu} + {}_{(1)}\eta_\mu\frac{\partial}{\partial z_\mu^{(1)}} + \dots + {}_{(k)}\eta_\mu\frac{\partial}{\partial z_\mu^{(k)}} \quad (\mu = n_d, \quad k \geq 0), \quad (17)$$

where for the zeroth-order prolongation ${}_{(0)}\mathcal{X} = \xi\frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \eta_\mu\frac{\partial}{\partial z_\mu}$, usually labeled as \mathcal{X} .

The evaluation of a given DE or system of DEs under the Infinitesimal Criterion for Invariance indicates whether or not there are admitted Lie symmetry transformations. This criterion simply follows as (OLIVERI, 2010; OVSIANNIKOV, 1982):

$${}_{(\sigma)}\mathcal{X}\{\mathcal{F}_n\} = 0, \quad \text{when } \mathcal{F}_n(x, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}^{\{1\}}, \dots, \mathbf{z}^{\{\sigma\}}) = 0 \quad (n = 1, 2, \dots, n_d), \quad (18)$$

which is parsed into a system of linear PDEs by grouping the terms with the same derivative order, known as the determining equations. The integration of such determining equations gives

⁸ $\beta_\mu\gamma_\mu = \sum_{i=1}^\mu \beta_i\gamma_i$.

the expressions of the infinitesimal functions in terms of x and \mathbf{z} and, hence, the Lie point transformations from the admitted Lie group. If a Lie group comprises a single transformation, it is called an one-parameter Lie group, otherwise a multiparameter Lie group. Computer algebra plays an essential role for solving determining equations, normally tiresome task, especially when dealing with high-order equations (VU; JEFFERSON; CARMINATI, 2012; DIMAS; TSOUBELIS, 2005; BAUMANN, 2000; HEREMAN, 1994).

If there is an one-parameter Lie group applicable to a DE, represented by the symmetry generator \mathcal{X} , one can set a change of variables associated with a new space of variables. The so-called invariants r , \mathbf{v} , $\mathbf{v}^{\{1\}}$, \dots , $\mathbf{v}^{\{\sigma\}}$ from the following relations express these new variables (BLUMAN, 1990):

$$\mathcal{X}\{r(x, \mathbf{z})\} = 0, \quad (1)\mathcal{X}\{\mathbf{v}(x, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}^{\{1\}})\} = 0, \quad (19)$$

and

$$({}^k)\mathcal{X}\{\mathbf{v}^{\{k-1\}}(x, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}^{\{1\}}, \dots, \mathbf{z}^{\{k\}})\} = 0 \quad (k = 2, 3, \dots, \sigma+1), \quad (20)$$

where $\mathbf{v} = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n_d})$.

After computing the full Lie group admitted by Eq. (14), a similar condition to Eq. (18) can be applied to the BCs of a given BVP in order to verify if it may represent a completely invariant BVP. Let \mathcal{S} be the number of boundary surfaces $s_i(x)$ of a BVP, then the invariance relations follow as (GAI; LI; SUDAO, 2020; CHERNIHA; KOVALENKO, 2012):

$$\mathcal{X}\{s_i(x)\} = 0, \quad \text{when } s_i = 0 \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{S}), \quad (21)$$

for all its BCs, denoted by \mathcal{B}_c :

$$({}^k)\mathcal{X}\{\mathcal{B}_c(x, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}^{\{1\}}, \dots, \mathbf{z}^{\{k\}})\} = 0, \quad \text{when } \mathcal{B}_c|_{s_i=0} = 0 \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{S}), \quad (22)$$

considering the non-prolonged symmetry generator \mathcal{X} for zero-order BCs, namely $\mathcal{B}_c(x, \mathbf{z}) = 0$.

5 Summary of Results

This section presents an overview of the current results of this study. First, the Lie symmetry method provides the admitted Lie symmetries for the mode shape equations of non-uniform rods, uniform Euler-Bernoulli and Timoshenko beams, and uniform rectangular plates. The non-uniform rods case details the symmetry and order reduction procedures. Reduced-order equations from new spaces of variables and exact closed-form solutions are provided for these mode shapes equations. Finally, this section presents a discussion on Lie symmetry methods for

non-uniform structures.

5.1 Order reduction and mode shapes of non-uniform rods

Let $\xi = \xi(x, u)$ and $\eta = \eta(x, u)$ ($n_d = 1$) be the infinitesimal functions associated with point transformations for Eq. (4). Accordingly, a second-order prolonged infinitesimal generator from Eq. (17) follows as:

$${}_{(2)}\mathcal{X} = \xi \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \eta \frac{\partial}{\partial u} + {}_{(1)}\eta \frac{\partial}{\partial u^{(1)}} + {}_{(2)}\eta \frac{\partial}{\partial u^{(2)}}. \quad (23)$$

This prolonged infinitesimal generator suits the infinitesimal criterion of Eq. (18) for Eq. (4), yielding the subsequent system of determining equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial u^2} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial u^2} - 2 \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x \partial u} + 2 \frac{S^{(1)}}{S} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial u} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x^2} - 2 \frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial x \partial u} - \frac{S^{(1)}}{S} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} - 3 \lambda^2 u \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial u} - \left[S^{(2)} - \frac{(S^{(1)})^2}{S} \right] \frac{\xi}{S} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial x^2} + \lambda^2 u \left(2 \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial u} \right) + \frac{S^{(1)}}{S} \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x} + \lambda^2 \eta &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

The infinitesimal functions from the solutions of Eq. (24), i.e., the admitted Lie symmetries, are given in Table 1. \mathcal{X}_2 represents a symmetry that depends on the specification of the function S to be explicitly computed, where Θ_1 and Θ_2 are arbitrary functions. Thus, the second symmetry is useless for reductions of the order unless S is a known function.

Table 1: Lie point symmetries for the mode shape equation of non-uniform rods

\mathcal{X}_i	$\xi_{(i)}$	$\eta_{(i)}$
\mathcal{X}_1	0	u
\mathcal{X}_2	$\Theta_1(x, u, S)$	$\Theta_2(x, u, S)$

Source: Prepared by the author.

The invariance relations Eqs. (19) and (20) lead to the set of invariants for the symmetry generator \mathcal{X}_1 :

$$\left\{ r = x, v = \frac{u^{(1)}}{u}, v^{(1)} = \frac{u^{(2)}}{u} - \left(\frac{u^{(1)}}{u} \right)^2 \right\}, \quad (25)$$

through which an order reduction is accomplished by a change of variables from the $(x, u, u^{(1)}, u^{(2)})$

to the $(r, v, v^{(1)})$ -space. From this, Eq. (4) is written as the following Riccati equation:

$$\frac{1}{S} \frac{d}{dr}(Sv) + v^2 + \lambda_0^2 = 0, \quad (26)$$

for $v=v(r)$ and $S=S(r)$ mentioned above. It is worth noticing that this first-order equation can replace the second-order Eq. (4) due to the existence of an admitted Lie symmetry transformation that, fundamentally, keeps the solution of the original equation invariant.

In the case of available closed-form solutions v for Eq. (26), mode shapes u can be recovered by the inverse transformation from the invariant relations $v=u^{(1)}/u$ and $r=x$ as follows:

$$u = e^{\int v dr}. \quad (27)$$

Within the context of such inverse mapped solutions, Appendix A.1 provides closed-form solutions for mode shapes functions of non-uniform rods in a table. Several cross-section variations have been considered, and some of them compared with solutions from the literature.

5.2 Exact numerically stable mode shapes of uniform Euler-Bernoulli beams

The Lie symmetries for the mode shape equation of uniform Euler-Bernoulli beams, Eq. (7), can be grouped such that there is a 6-parameter infinitesimal generator:

$$\mathcal{X} = \left(u + \alpha_1 e^{\lambda x} + \alpha_2 e^{-\lambda x} + \alpha_3 \sin(\lambda x) + \alpha_4 \cos(\lambda x) \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial u} + \alpha_5 \frac{\partial}{\partial x}, \quad (28)$$

for the transformation parameters $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4$, and α_5 . From the invariance formulation for BVPs when considering the infinitesimal generator from Eq. (28), Eq. (21) requires $\alpha_5 = 0$ in order to have an invariant surface for any BCs at $x=l_i$ ($i = 1, 2$). In addition to that, Table 2 shows the invariance relations from Eq. (22) for classical and non-classical BCs, whose evaluation leads to the restriction equations from the right column. Here, $u^{(1)}$, $EI u^{(2)}$ and $-EI u^{(3)}$ denote, respectively, slope, bending moment and shearing force (WEAVER; TIMOSHENKO; YOUNG, 1990). For added impedances, translational and rotational stiffnesses are denoted by $K_{i,T}$ and $K_{i,R}$, respectively, translational masses are given by m_i , and rotational inertias by J_i , $\mathcal{M}_i = -K_{i,R} + (EI/\rho S) J_i \lambda^4$ and $\mathcal{V}_i = -K_{i,T} + (EI/\rho S) m_i \lambda^4$, and $b_1 = -1$ and $b_2 = 1$ represent the convention for positive and negative signs at the left and the right ends of the beam, respectively (KARNOVSKY; LEBED, 2004; WANG; REDDY; LEE, 2000).

Appendix A.2 displays exact solutions that do not suffer from numerical instabilities for mode shapes of uniform Euler-Bernoulli beams subject to classical and non-classical BCs. Clamped ($u = 0, u^{(1)} = 0$) $|_{x=l_i}$, free ($EI u^{(2)} = 0, EI u^{(3)} = 0$) $|_{x=l_i}$, pinned ($u = 0, EI u^{(2)} = 0$) $|_{x=l_i}$, and sliding ($u^{(1)} = 0, EI u^{(3)} = 0$) $|_{x=l_i}$ end combinations have been considered, while beams with non-classical conditions are given in terms of impedance values.

Table 2: Invariance relations for BCs of Euler-Bernoulli beams

Invariance relations ($x = l_i$)	Restriction equation
$\mathcal{X}\{u\}=0$	$\alpha_1 e^{\lambda l_i} + \alpha_2 e^{-\lambda l_i} + \alpha_3 \sin(\lambda l_i) + \alpha_4 \cos(\lambda l_i) = 0$
${}_{(1)}\mathcal{X}\{u^{(1)}\}=0$	$-\alpha_1 e^{\lambda l_i} + \alpha_2 e^{-\lambda l_i} - \alpha_3 \cos(\lambda l_i) + \alpha_4 \sin(\lambda l_i) = 0$
${}_{(2)}\mathcal{X}\{EI u^{(2)} - b_i \mathcal{M}_i u^{(1)}\}=0$	$\alpha_1 \left(\lambda - b_i \frac{\mathcal{M}_i}{EI} \right) e^{\lambda l_i} + \alpha_2 \left(\lambda + b_i \frac{\mathcal{M}_i}{EI} \right) e^{-\lambda l_i} - \left(\alpha_3 \lambda - \alpha_4 b_i \frac{\mathcal{M}_i}{EI} \right) \sin(\lambda l_i) - \left(\alpha_4 \lambda + \alpha_3 b_i \frac{\mathcal{M}_i}{EI} \right) \cos(\lambda l_i) = 0$
${}_{(3)}\mathcal{X}\{EI u^{(3)} + b_i \mathcal{V}_i u\}=0$	$\alpha_1 \left(\lambda^3 + b_i \frac{\mathcal{V}_i}{EI} \right) e^{\lambda l_i} - \alpha_2 \left(\lambda^3 - b_i \frac{\mathcal{V}_i}{EI} \right) e^{-\lambda l_i} + \left(\alpha_4 \lambda^3 + \alpha_3 b_i \frac{\mathcal{V}_i}{EI} \right) \sin(\lambda l_i) - \left(\alpha_3 \lambda^3 - \alpha_4 b_i \frac{\mathcal{V}_i}{EI} \right) \cos(\lambda l_i) = 0$

Source: Prepared by the author.

As an example, Figure 1 shows the 1st and 15th mode shapes of a clamped-free beam, computed by the Lie symmetry approach (solid lines) and the corresponding classical solution from the literature (dashed lines) (INMAN, 2013; GERADIN, 2015). In this case, a beam of length $l = 1$ m for $x \in [0, l]$ having the following properties has been considered: cross-sectional area $S = 2.5 \times 10^{-4}$ m², Young's modulus $E = 70$ GPa, inertia moment $I = 5.2 \times 10^{-10}$ m⁴ and density $\rho = 2.7 \times 10^3$ kg/m³. It is clearly shown that the proposed approach is able to describe the beam mode shapes without round-off errors even at high frequencies, contrary to the classical approach.

Figure 1: 1st and 15th mode shapes of a uniform clamped-free beam computed via the Lie symmetry approach (blue solid line) and the classical approach (black dashed line)

5.3 Reduced-order mode shape equations for uniform Timoshenko beams

The following two infinitesimal generators were selected from Lie group of admitted transformations for the mode shape equations of uniform Timoshenko beams. The constants associated

to them are given by Eqs. (30) and (31).

$$\mathcal{X}_1 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x}, \quad \mathcal{X}_3 = e^{c_1 x} \frac{\partial}{\partial u} + c_1 c_3 e^{c_1 x} \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi}, \quad (29)$$

and the constants:

$$c_1 = \sqrt{-\frac{\lambda^2 (\beta + 1) + c_5}{2\beta}}, \quad (30)$$

$$c_3 = \frac{\lambda^2 (\beta - 1) + 2\gamma - c_5}{2(\gamma - \lambda^2)}, \quad (31)$$

$$c_3 = \frac{\lambda^2 (\beta - 1) + 2\gamma - c_5}{2(\gamma - \lambda^2)}, \quad (32)$$

$$c_4 = \frac{\lambda^2 (\beta - 1) + 2\gamma + c_5}{2(\gamma - \lambda^2)}, \quad (33)$$

$$c_5 = \lambda \sqrt{\lambda^2 (\beta - 1)^2 + 4\beta\gamma}, \quad (34)$$

for $\beta = E/G\kappa$, $\gamma = A/I$ and $\lambda = (\rho/G\kappa)^{\frac{1}{2}} \omega$.

The two second-order ODEs from Eqs. (10) and (11) require two order reductions to be converted into two first-order ODEs once each Lie symmetry is capable of reducing by one the order of a single equation from the system. In order to do that, \mathcal{X}_3 and \mathcal{X}_1 were considered for the first and the second reductions, respectively⁹. Then, the mode shape equations for uniform Timoshenko beams are written in the $(\overset{2}{r}, \overset{2}{v}, \overset{2}{\psi}, \overset{2}{v}^{(1)}, \overset{2}{\psi}^{(1)})$ -space of variables as follows through the two successive order reductions:

$$\overset{2}{\psi} \left(\overset{2}{v}^{(1)} - 1 \right) + \frac{c_1 c_2^2}{c_6} \overset{2}{v} = 0, \quad (35)$$

and

$$\overset{2}{\psi} \left(c_1 c_4 \overset{2}{v}^{(1)} + \overset{2}{\psi}^{(1)} \right) - c_6 \left(c_3 \overset{2}{v} + \overset{2}{r} \right) = 0, \quad (36)$$

where $\overset{2}{v} = \overset{2}{v}(\overset{2}{r})$, $\overset{2}{\psi} = \overset{2}{\psi}(\overset{2}{r})$, and $c_6 = \frac{c_1^2 + c_2^2}{2 - (c_3 + c_4)}$.

The resolution of the system of reduced-order equations from Eqs. (35) and (36) yields the same closed-form solutions of mode shapes of Timoshenko beams (KHASAWNEH; SEGALMAN, 2019; CAZZANI; STOCHINO; TURCO, 2016). Here, the advantage of having first-order ODEs instead of the original ones is that the reduced equations are tougher to solve via symbolic methods. Although symmetry reductions from the set $\{\mathcal{X}_3, \mathcal{X}_1\}$ result in the adversity as mentioned above, other infinitesimal generators can be taken from admitted Lie group of transformations

⁹Depending on the structure of the Lie algebra, there is a preferential ordering for using the associated symmetries, namely the chain of subalgebras from the solvable Lie algebra (BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002; HYDON, 1998).

and applied to get new reduced mode shape equations.

5.4 Invariant solutions for the mode shape equation of uniform rectangular plates

From the set of 12 computed Lie symmetries for Eq. (13), the three following infinitesimal generators provide valid invariant solutions:

$$\mathcal{X}_1 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x}, \quad \mathcal{X}_2 = \frac{\partial}{\partial y}, \quad \mathcal{X}_5 = e^{-\lambda x} \frac{\partial}{\partial w}. \quad (37)$$

In contrast with all the previous mode shape equations in this section, the mode shape equation for rectangular plates consists in a PDE. The order reduction procedure for PDEs through Lie symmetry transformations compresses the given equation's space of variables, reducing their number of independent variables by one. Once Eq. (13) has 2 independent variables, each symmetry provides an ODE by compressing the two independent variables into a single new coordinate. The resolution of such ODEs leads to the subsequent invariant solutions:

$$w_1 = \mathcal{C}_1 e^{\lambda x} + \mathcal{C}_2 e^{-\lambda x} + \mathcal{C}_3 \sin(\lambda x) + \mathcal{C}_4 \cos(\lambda x), \quad (38)$$

$$w_2 = \mathcal{C}_5 e^{\lambda y} + \mathcal{C}_6 e^{-\lambda y} + \mathcal{C}_7 \sin(\lambda y) + \mathcal{C}_8 \cos(\lambda y), \quad (39)$$

$$w_3 = \mathcal{C}_9 I_0\left(\lambda\sqrt{x^2+y^2}\right) + \mathcal{C}_{10} J_0\left(\lambda\sqrt{x^2+y^2}\right) + \mathcal{C}_{11} K_0\left(\lambda\sqrt{x^2+y^2}\right) + \mathcal{C}_{12} Y_0\left(\lambda\sqrt{x^2+y^2}\right), \quad (40)$$

where \mathcal{C}_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 12$) are real constants which follow from the BCs of the plate, J_0 and Y_0 are Bessel functions of the first and second kinds and I_0 and K_0 are the modified Bessel functions of the first and second kinds, respectively.

The three solutions from Eqs. (38-40) are exact solutions of Eq. (13), although not suitable for BVPs when considering each one independently. Superimposing invariant solutions for linear equations is a well-known method for finding closed-form solutions for PDEs (SAEIDIFAR; OHADI, 2010; BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002; SESHADRI; NA, 1985). The superposition may assemble solutions that could fit any BC for a given plate if its BCs are invariant under the same Lie point transformations applied to the reduction procedure, then obtain exact mode shape solutions for rectangular plates. This research currently studies the invariance formulation for BCs when dealing with such Lie transformations, aiming at suitable original, exact, solutions for vibrating rectangular plates subject to all kinds of BCs.

5.5 Lie symmetries of non-uniform beams and plates

About non-uniform Euler-Bernoulli beams, the computation of Lie symmetries for Eq. (6) yield the same Lie group admitted by the mode shape equation of non-uniform rods, i.e., the

Lie point transformations from Table 1. The order reduction procedure leads to a third-order ODE through \mathcal{X}_1 from the table mentioned above, and \mathcal{X}_2 remains as a useless transformation. Solving a third-order ODE instead of a fourth-order one, both with the same level of complexity, may not represent significant progress aiming to compute exact mode shapes of non-uniform beams. Once each symmetry may provide a single reduction of order, one can see that there are insufficient symmetry transformations for converting Eq. (6) into a first-order ODE, then being completely integrable by the Lie symmetry method. Correspondingly, many equations lack Lie point transformations or admit insufficient symmetries to completely integrate them (MENDOZA; MURIEL, 2021; NUCCI, 2008; GONZÁLEZ-LÓPEZ, 1988). In this circumstance, alternative symmetry methods help compute comprehensive symmetry transformations, enabling the complete integration of such DEs under study.

The complexity of the mode shape equations for non-uniform Timoshenko beams is translated into complicated determining equations. Thus, the Lie symmetry calculation for these mode shape equations requires significant computational effort, lowering the efficiency of the method. Notice that this discussion leads to “better conditioned” symmetry methods as alternatives, emphasizing the generalized symmetry method. The mode shape equation for non-uniform plates can be taken from the same perspective, requiring better-structured symmetry methods for dealing with its arbitrary functions, which provide transformations that act on broader spaces of variables.

6 Work Plan

This research project is organized in the following 5 steps and carried out during 24 months, whose distribution through eight trimesters is shown in Tab. 3.

1. Study on the superposition of invariant solutions for assessing exact mode shape functions for uniform rectangular plates through invariant admitted BCs, preparation and submission of a manuscript to the Journal of Sound and Vibration reporting the accomplished new exact solution. Regardless of being suitable for every possible BC of a given plate, the Lie symmetry method provides new invariant solutions not reported in the literature yet.
2. Literature review on the generalized symmetry method for ODEs and PDEs, focusing on reduction order procedures for DEs with arbitrary functions. The main challenge of this step relies on studying complex mathematical approaches based on abstract algebra and the Group Theory. It is worth emphasizing the mathematical support planned for a BEPE internship with Prof. Dr. Adrián S. Ruiz’s and Prof. Dr. María C. Muriel Patino’s collaboration at the University of Cádiz. Part of this step may be executed during a BEPE

internship at the University of Cádiz.

3. Assessment of generalized symmetries of non-uniform beams and plates, which hasn't been explored so far in the literature, proposition of reduced-order equations, and exact mode shape solutions. This is the very original point of this proposal.
4. Within the results for non-uniform structures, real complex problems just as periodic and metamaterial structures will be investigated following the same procedure, aiming at problems with no exact solutions in the literature.
5. Thesis preparation, submission of research articles, definition of prospects and research collaborations.

Table 3: Trimester (T) execution schedule

Step	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T6	T7	T8	T9	T10	T11	T12
1	•	•										
2			•	•	•	•						
3				•	•	•	•	•				
4								•	•	•	•	
5								•	•	•	•	•

Source: Prepared by the author.

7 About the Candidate

The candidate Afonso Willian Nunes completed his bachelor's mechanical engineering degree¹⁰ in December of 2019, attending the mechanical engineering master's program at UNESP, Ilha Solteira, since March of 2020. While undergraduate, the student presented the following achievements:

- No failures in the disciplines, as shown in the academic register¹¹, achieving the performance coefficient of 8.29 in the course, and five certificates of best student in class and two awards at the graduation ceremony¹².
- Scientific Initiation scholarship provided by FAPESP for 24 months, grant number 2016/22473-6, related to the study and application of Lie symmetries in engineering problems such as

¹⁰https://www.dropbox.com/sh/22aygal2f4vmbjd/AACRmAoOMvE39QHfL6_niUna?dl=0

¹¹https://www.dropbox.com/sh/3rwq44da33ijte7/AAAC-H4rrvzioZqd4J0Le_vEa?dl=0

¹²https://www.dropbox.com/sh/ogv4ock438f0vsl/AADoP_GP4-04bK1y2KTI-cgOa?dl=0

the deflection of beams and wave propagation in structures, yielding conference papers¹³ at *Conferência Brasileira de Dinâmica, Controle e Aplicações* (DINCON 2017), *X Congresso Nacional de Engenharia Mecânica* (CONEM 2018) and *VI Symposium of Intelligent Materials and Control* (SYMC 2018) as well as the conference presentations¹⁴ and two honorable mentions¹⁵ among the best research of *Simpósio Internacional de Iniciação Científica e Tecnológica da Universidade de São Paulo* (SIICUSP 2017) and *XXX Congresso de Iniciação Científica da Unesp* (CIC 2018).

- BEPE Internship from January to February of 2019 in Blois, France, at INSA Centre Val de Loire, grant number 2018/21734-6, supervised by Prof. Dr. Jean-Mathieu Mencik, who afterward wrote a recommendation letter¹⁶ concerning the student qualities. The research project has led to a congress paper¹⁷ orally presented in the International Congress of Mechanical Engineering (COBEM 2019), held in Uberlândia, MG.

In the same way, the student had been attending the master's program¹⁸ competently:

- Excellent grades (A) in all attended disciplines, as given in the master's academic record¹⁹.
- Manuscript submitted to the journal *Acta Mechanica* (publisher Springer Nature, impact factor 2.698 in 2020) entitled "Stable computation of mode shapes of uniform Euler-Bernoulli beams subject to classical and non-classical BCs via Lie symmetries," developed and written in collaboration with this project's supervisor, Prof. Dr. Samuel da Silva, Prof. Dr. Jean-Mathieu Mencik, and Prof. Dr. Paulo J. Paupitz.
- Master's scholarship from the National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq), grant number 131846/2020-5, from 01/03/2020 to 28/02/2022.
- General Qualification Examination (EGQ) presented and approved on 17/09/2021.

¹³<https://www.dropbox.com/sh/tot71lwapdx0cxv/AADBtwGDm-cBodppiuNdHXi4a?dl=0>

¹⁴https://www.dropbox.com/sh/i39twhtnosrvrt2/AAAd4C-QQjqELJlnqbH5wPu_a?dl=0

¹⁵<https://www.dropbox.com/sh/e8ijry5g3qsicl2/AACgC5jzs7Uf34Nwz4V7lOnva?dl=0>

¹⁶<https://www.dropbox.com/sh/547f8adwsxv1dco/AADmmGMW3Umk9PKuMlsNm2Psa?dl=0>

¹⁷https://www.dropbox.com/sh/kesbz4kgik57wpg/AABpvXwVanfZnKBSsek1XGL_a?dl=0

¹⁸https://www.dropbox.com/sh/akfwo5bq1knc1w/AABf6MjZxj-UyAH2pPq3IVa_ja?dl=0

¹⁹<https://www.dropbox.com/sh/k2yvlyicg5oxrvx/AADZjjNyyVmzi4xDyvrjQFY0a?dl=0>

Appendix

A.1 Closed-form mode shape solutions for non-uniform rods

Table 4: Closed-form mode shape solutions for rods with non-uniform cross-sections

Cross-section area function $S(x)$	Inverse-mapped closed-form solution $u(x)$	Solutions issued from the literature
a_0+a_1x	$C_1 K_0\left(-j\frac{\lambda_0}{a_1}(a_0+a_1x)\right) + C_2 J_0\left(\frac{\lambda_0}{a_1}(a_0+a_1x)\right)$	similar to Kumar and Sujith (1997) and Hull (2018)
$a_2x^2+a_4x^4$	$\frac{C_1}{x} H_c\left(0, -\frac{1}{2}, 0, -\frac{\lambda_0^2 a_2}{4 a_4}, \frac{\lambda_0^2 a_2}{4 a_4} - 1, -\frac{a_4 x^2}{a_2}\right) + C_2 H_c\left(0, \frac{1}{2}, 0, -\frac{\lambda_0^2 a_2}{4 a_4}, \frac{\lambda_0^2 a_2}{4 a_4} - 1, -\frac{a_4 x^2}{a_2}\right)$	different from Kumar and Sujith (1997)
$(a_0+a_1x)^n$	$(a_0+a_1)^{\frac{1-n}{2}} \left(C_1 K_{-\frac{1-n}{2}}\left(-j\frac{\lambda_0}{a_1}(a_0+a_1x)\right) + C_2 I_{-\frac{1-n}{2}}\left(-j\frac{\lambda_0}{a_1}(a_0+a_1x)\right) \right)$	similar to Kumar and Sujith (1997), more general than Abrate (1995)
$a_0 a_1^{a_2 x}$	$C_1 a_2^{-\frac{a_3}{2} x} \cos\left(\sqrt{4\lambda_0^2 - (\ln(a_2) a_3)^2} \frac{x - C_1}{2}\right) + C_2$	more general than Guo and Yang (2011b)
$a_0 \sin(a_1+a_2x)$	$C_1 \cos(a_1+a_2x) {}_2F_1\left(-\frac{\sqrt{4\lambda_0^2+a_2^2}-3a_2}{4a_2}, \frac{\sqrt{4\lambda_0^2+a_2^2}+3a_2}{4a_2}; \frac{3}{2}; \cos^2(a_1+a_2x)\right) +$ $C_2 {}_2F_1\left(-\frac{\sqrt{4\lambda_0^2+a_2^2}-a_2}{4a_2}, \frac{\sqrt{4\lambda_0^2+a_2^2}+a_2}{4a_2}; \frac{1}{2}; \cos^2(a_1+a_2x)\right)$	subclass from Yardimoglu and Aydin (2011)
$a_0 \left(\frac{\cos(a_1+a_2x)}{\cos(a_1)}\right)^2$	$\frac{1}{\cos(a_1+a_2x)} (C_1 \cosh(\sqrt{-a_2^2-\lambda_0^2}x) + C_2 \sinh(\sqrt{-a_2^2-\lambda_0^2}x))$	series solution from Guo and Yang (2011b)
$a_0 \sinh(a_1+a_2x)$	$C_1 Q_{\frac{\sqrt{-4\lambda_0^2+a_2^2}-a_2}}{2a_2} \left(\cosh(a_1+a_2x)\right) + C_2 P_{\frac{\sqrt{-4\lambda_0^2+a_2^2}-a_2}}{2a_2} \left(\cosh(a_1+a_2x)\right)$	—
$a_0 \cosh(a_1+a_2x)$	$C_1 \sinh(a_1+a_2x) {}_2F_1\left(-\frac{j\sqrt{4\lambda_0^2-a_2^2}-3a_2}{4a_2}, \frac{j\sqrt{4\lambda_0^2-a_2^2}+3a_2}{4a_2}; \frac{3}{2}; -\sinh^2(a_1+a_2x)\right) +$ $C_2 {}_2F_1\left(-\frac{j\sqrt{4\lambda_0^2-a_2^2}-a_2}{4a_2}, \frac{j\sqrt{4\lambda_0^2-a_2^2}+a_2}{4a_2}; \frac{1}{2}; -\sinh^2(a_1+a_2x)\right)$	—
$a_0 \left(\frac{\cosh(a_1+a_2x)}{\cosh(a_1)}\right)^2$	$\frac{1}{\cosh(a_1+a_2x)} (C_1 \cosh(\sqrt{a_2^2-\lambda_0^2}x) + C_2 \sinh(\sqrt{a_2^2-\lambda_0^2}x))$	series solution from Guo and Yang (2011b)
$a_0+a_1P_0(a_3x)$	$C_1 \cos(\lambda_0(C_2+x))$	—
$a_0+a_1P_1(a_3x)$	$C_1 K_0\left(-j\frac{\lambda_0}{a_1 a_3}(a_0+a_1 a_3 x)\right) + C_2 J_0\left(\frac{\lambda_0}{a_1 a_3}(a_0+a_1 a_3 x)\right)$	—

I_μ - first kind modified Bessel function of order μ ; K_μ - second kind modified Bessel function of order μ ; J_μ - first kind Bessel function of order μ ;
 H_c - Heun confluent function; ${}_2F_1$ hypergeometric function; P_μ - first kind Legendre function of order μ ; Q_μ - second kind Legendre function of order μ

Source: Prepared by the author.

Exact implicit solutions can be computed when considering high-order polynomials, Jacobi functions, combined hyperbolic functions, and products of polynomials and exponential functions, which are not presented here.

A.2 Numerically stable mode shapes of Euler-Bernoulli beams

Table 5: Mode shapes of uniform Euler-Bernoulli beams with classical BCs

	$\alpha_1 e^{\lambda x}$	$\alpha_2 e^{-\lambda x}$	$\alpha_3 \sin(\lambda x)$	$\alpha_4 \cos(\lambda x)$	λl
clamped-clamped 	$\frac{sc^+ + e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - es^+} e^{\lambda(x-l)}$	$-\frac{1 - sc^+ e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - es^+} e^{-\lambda x}$	$-\frac{1 + ec^-}{1 - es^-} \sin(\lambda x)$	$\cos(\lambda x)$	$\lambda_1 l = 4.7300407$ $\lambda_2 l = 7.8532046$ $\lambda_3 l = 10.9956078$ $\lambda_4 l = 14.1371655$
free-free 	$-\frac{sc^- + e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - es^-} e^{\lambda(x-l)}$	$\frac{1 - sc^- e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - es^-} e^{-\lambda x}$	$-\frac{1 + ec^+}{1 - es^+} \sin(\lambda x)$	$\cos(\lambda x)$	$\lambda_5 l = 17.2787596$ $\lambda_n l \approx (2n+1) \frac{\pi}{2}, n > 5$
clamped-pinned 	$\frac{sc^+ + e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - es^+} e^{\lambda(x-l)}$	$-\frac{1 - sc^+ e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - es^+} e^{-\lambda x}$	$-\frac{1 + ec^-}{1 - es^-} \sin(\lambda x)$	$\cos(\lambda x)$	$\lambda_1 l = 3.9266023$ $\lambda_2 l = 7.0685827$ $\lambda_3 l = 10.2101761$ $\lambda_4 l = 13.3517688$
free-pinned 	$\frac{sc^- - e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - es^-} e^{\lambda(x-l)}$	$\frac{1 + sc^- e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - es^-} e^{-\lambda x}$	$-\frac{1 + ec^+}{1 - es^+} \sin(\lambda x)$	$\cos(\lambda x)$	$\lambda_5 l = 16.4933614$ $\lambda_n l \approx (4n+1) \frac{\pi}{4}, n > 5$
clamped-sliding 	$\frac{sc^+ - e^{-\lambda l}}{1 + ec^+} e^{\lambda(x-l)}$	$-\frac{1 + sc^+ e^{-\lambda l}}{1 + ec^+} e^{-\lambda x}$	$-\frac{1 - es^-}{1 + ec^-} \sin(\lambda x)$	$\cos(\lambda x)$	$\lambda_1 l = 2.3650204$ $\lambda_2 l = 5.497804$ $\lambda_3 l = 8.6393798$ $\lambda_4 l = 11.7809724$
free-sliding 	$\frac{sc^- + e^{-\lambda l}}{1 + ec^-} e^{\lambda(x-l)}$	$\frac{1 - sc^- e^{-\lambda l}}{1 + ec^-} e^{-\lambda x}$	$-\frac{1 - es^+}{1 + ec^+} \sin(\lambda x)$	$\cos(\lambda x)$	$\lambda_5 l = 14.9225651$ $\lambda_n l \approx (4n-1) \frac{\pi}{4}, n > 5$
clamped-free 	$-\frac{sc^- - e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - es^-} e^{\lambda(x-l)}$	$-\frac{1 + sc^- e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - es^-} e^{-\lambda x}$	$-\frac{1 + ec^+}{1 - es^+} \sin(\lambda x)$	$\cos(\lambda x)$	$\lambda_1 l = 1.8751041$ $\lambda_2 l = 4.6940911$ $\lambda_3 l = 7.8547574$ $\lambda_4 l = 10.9955407$ $\lambda_5 l = 14.1371684$ $\lambda_n l \approx (2n-1) \frac{\pi}{2}, n > 5$

$$\begin{aligned}
 sc^+ &= \sin(\lambda l) + \cos(\lambda l), & es^+ &= (e^{-\lambda l} + 2 \sin(\lambda l)) e^{-\lambda l}, & ec^+ &= (e^{-\lambda l} + 2 \cos(\lambda l)) e^{-\lambda l}, \\
 sc^- &= \sin(\lambda l) - \cos(\lambda l), & es^- &= (e^{-\lambda l} - 2 \sin(\lambda l)) e^{-\lambda l}, & ec^- &= (e^{-\lambda l} - 2 \cos(\lambda l)) e^{-\lambda l}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Source: Prepared by the author.

Table 6: Mode shapes of uniform Euler-Bernoulli beams with non-classical BCs

	general non-classical boundaries
$\alpha_1 e^{\lambda x}$	$\left\{ \left(\lambda + \frac{\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \right) \left(EI \lambda^4 + \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} \nu_1 \right) e^{-\lambda l} + \left[-EI \lambda^5 + (2\mathcal{M}_1 + \mathcal{M}_2) \lambda^4 + \frac{\mathcal{M}_1 + 2\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \nu_1 \lambda - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1 \mathcal{M}_2}{(EI)^2} \nu_1 \right] \cos(\lambda l) \right. \\ \left. + \left[EI \lambda^5 + (\mathcal{M}_2 \lambda^2 + 2\nu_1) \lambda^2 - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} (2\mathcal{M}_2 \lambda^2 + \nu_1) \lambda - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1 \mathcal{M}_2}{(EI)^2} \nu_1 \right] \sin(\lambda l) \right\} \frac{e^{\lambda(x-l)}}{\alpha_0}$
$\alpha_2 e^{-\lambda x}$	$\left\{ - \left(\lambda - \frac{\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \right) \left(EI \lambda^4 + \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} \nu_1 \right) + \left[EI \lambda^5 + (2\mathcal{M}_1 + \mathcal{M}_2) \lambda^4 - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1 + 2\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \nu_1 \lambda - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1 \mathcal{M}_2}{(EI)^2} \nu_1 \right] e^{-\lambda l} \cos(\lambda l) \right. \\ \left. + \left[EI \lambda^5 - (\mathcal{M}_2 \lambda^2 + 2\nu_1) \lambda^2 - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} (2\mathcal{M}_2 \lambda^2 + \nu_1) \lambda + \frac{\mathcal{M}_1 \mathcal{M}_2}{(EI)^2} \nu_1 \right] e^{-\lambda l} \sin(\lambda l) \right\} \frac{e^{-\lambda x}}{\alpha_0}$
$\alpha_3 \sin(\lambda x)$	$\left[\left(\lambda - \frac{\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \right) \left(EI \lambda^4 + 2\nu_1 \lambda - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} \nu_1 \right) + \left(\lambda + \frac{\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \right) \left(EI \lambda^4 - 2\nu_1 \lambda - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} \nu_1 \right) e^{-2kl} \right. \\ \left. - 2 \left(\lambda \cos(\lambda l) - \frac{\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \sin(\lambda l) \right) \left(EI \lambda^4 + \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} \nu_1 \right) e^{-\lambda l} \right] \frac{\sin(\lambda x)}{\alpha_0}$
$\alpha_4 \cos(\lambda x)$	$\cos(\lambda x)$
α_0	$\left[- \left(\lambda - \frac{\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \right) \left(EI \lambda^4 - 2\mathcal{M}_1 \lambda^3 - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} \nu_1 \right) + \left(\lambda + \frac{\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \right) \left(EI \lambda^4 + 2\mathcal{M}_1 \lambda^3 - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} \nu_1 \right) e^{-2kl} \right. \\ \left. + 2 \left(\lambda \sin(\lambda l) + \frac{\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \cos(\lambda l) \right) \left(EI \lambda^4 + \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} \nu_1 \right) e^{-\lambda l} \right]$

Source: Prepared by the author.

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